

Template 1 - Load and extract surfaces

Template to load and extract the surfaces/incisions from the 2.5 point mesh acquired with the 3D scanner.

Artefact: Manot

1. Load 2.5 point mesh

Surface 1

Surface 2

Identity card

Name:	manot_cut_aligned_a...v2 - Topography layer		
File path:	?		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	28.24	mm	
Size:	1589	points	
Spacing:	17.78	µm	
Offset:	-6.70	mm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	40.16	mm	
Size:	1117	points	
Spacing:	35.99	µm	
Offset:	-22.33	mm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	4.081	mm	
Min:	29.95	mm	
Max:	34.04	mm	
Size:	40813002	digits	
Spacing:	0.0001	µm	
NM-points ratio:	31.49 % (558840 Pts)		

Identity card

Name:	manot_cut_aligned_2aoi_v2		
File path:	H:\Manotpa...\manot_cut_aligned_2aoi_v2.stl		
Studiable type:	Surface+image		
Axis:	X		
Length:	27.88	mm	
Size:	2000	points	
Spacing:	13.95	µm	
Offset:	-8.096	mm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	50.58	mm	
Size:	1102	points	
Spacing:	45.94	µm	
Offset:	-20.72	mm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	6.711	mm	
Min:	23.94	mm	
Max:	30.65	mm	
Size:	67105356	digits	
Spacing:	0.0001	µm	
NM-points ratio:	25.09 % (552973 Pts)		
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Image (grayscale)		
Min:	0.000		
Max:	65535		

2. Extract Areas of Interest (AOI)

AOI1

AOI2

AOI3

Level

AOI1

AOI2

AOI3

4. Extract individual areas/incisions from each AOI

manot_AOI2_inci3

manot_AOI2_inci4

manot_AOI3_inci1

manot_AOI3_inci2

manot_AOI3_inci3

manot_AOI3_inci4

manot_AOI3_inci5

manot_AOI3_inci6

manot_AOI3_inci7

manot_AOI3_inci8

manot_AOI3_inci9

manot_AOI3_inci10

manot_AOI3_inci11

manot_AOI3_inci12

manot_AOI3_inci13

manot_AOI3_inci14

4. Workflow

